

Rubella Virus and Congenital Birth Defects in Bangladesh: A Study of Social Determinants

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ABSTRACT

This study which is basically quantitative in nature was conducted to explore the determinants of social awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects in the study areas. A survey questionnaire, for such purpose, was designed and different statistical methods were applied to analyze the collected data. Also, qualitative technique like FGD was used to validate the study. After analyzing data, finally the study finds that social awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects were significantly associated with three determinants such as household income, perceived susceptibility and watching NTV Program by Mehroz Alom on Rubella complication. The study also finds the lack of social awareness regarding the risks of Rubella virus on the foetus¹.

Key Words: Rubella Virus, Congenital Birth Defects, Social Determinants.

INTRODUCTION

Rubella virus is a major public health problem in Bangladesh, which is as infectious as flu affecting all ages and sexes^{4,14} especially pregnant women. The most devastating aftermaths of rubella infection during pregnancy are abortion, stillbirth, and foetal malformation that arise from maternal infection during the first trimester of pregnancy. If the pregnant woman catches rubella during 1st trimester (up to week 13 of the pregnancy), there is an 80% probability that the foetus will also be infected.⁵ The rubella infection can easily pass to the foetus and also cause birth defects, which is known as CRS (Congenital Rubella Syndrome), causing cataracts including other eye defects, deafness, heart abnormalities, a small head, mental retardation, a slower than normal growth rate, and the injuries in the brain, liver and lungs.^{20,21} However, the

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probability that the foetus will have birth defects depends on the period of pregnant woman's infection. If she catches rubella during weeks 8-10 of the pregnancy, there is a 90% probability that the foetus will have birth defects.²⁷ Though the impact of Rubella virus is devastating in our country, both the government and the people of Bangladesh are less aware of this virus. Also, the role of electronic media is not satisfactory to make the social awareness regarding this important health issue.

STUDY RATIONALE

The worldwide epidemic of rubella in 1962-65 drew attention to the significance of CRS. During rubella eruptions, rates of CRS per 1000 live births were at least 1.7 in Israel, 1.7 in Jamaica, 0.7 in Oman, 2.2 in Panama, 1.5 in Singapore, 0.9 in Sri Lanka, and 0.6 in Trinidad and Tobago. According to the study findings in 45 developing countries, the proportion of women who remained susceptible to rubella (e.g. seronegative) was <10% in 13 countries, 10-24% in 20 countries, and 25% in 12 countries.^{8,9,15,24} Bangladesh is no more Rubella virus free country but very few people are aware of Rubella IgG and IgM antibodies. A study that was performed in BSMMU (Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University) to identify the seroprevalence of rubella IgG among the antenatal population attending a tertiary level hospital in Bangladesh shows that Sera from 609 pregnant women were tested for rubella IgG antibody using ELISA (Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay) technique. 85.9% were seropositive and 14.1% were seronegative. The prevalence of the antibody was 80% between 15 and 20 years of age. This figure gradually increased with age until it peaked at 90.2% in the age group of 31-36 years. Then the seropositivity decreased to 81.3% in the age group of >36 years. No statistically significant difference of seroprevalence was found among housewives and service-holders (Ashrafunnessa et. al., 2000).^{2,3}

Ashrafunnessa et. al. (2008) in their study on urban and rural Bangladeshi women show that in a total of 582 children and women in the child bearing age, the average prevalence of Rubella antibody was 71.99 % and that of IgG increased gradually with age.³

Another study conducted by Rahman et. al. (2002) shows that a total of 198 hearing-impaired children and 200 children without hearing problems were studied. After taking a detailed history from the parents, blood samples were collected from both mothers and children; sera were subjected to ELISA for anti-rubella IgG. Rubella antibody was detected in 74% of the hearing-impaired children and in 18% of those with normal

hearing: this finding correlated with the presence of rubella antibody in the mothers (67%) of rubella seropositive hearing-impaired children. Consistent with the presence of antibody, 41% of the seropositive mothers who had hearing-impaired children gave a history of fever and rash during early pregnancy.¹⁹ As Secretary General of Pediatric Cardiac Society of Bangladesh says, in Bangladesh, approximately 25,000 to 30,000 children are born with congenital heart diseases and 90 per cent of these children die before their fifth birthday. But the treatment facilities for the large number of children are still very poor and relatively under-focused (bangladesh2day).^{2,3,19} The above studies indicate that rubella infection is not only common in Bangladesh but also endemic like many other countries. In addition, the results of these studies also indicate the need for a national immunization programme. This plight requires leaders from communities, civil society, mass media, nations and regions to come together in concerned, coordinated action to fight against Rubella virus. Both electronic and print media should run the awareness program concerning this issue.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the present study is to unearth the factors influencing social awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects. To achieve this objective, the study intends:

1. to explore the socio-demographic profile of the respondents;
2. to determine the degree of association between social awareness regarding Rubella virus and selected socio-demographic factors;
3. to find out the relationship between the respondents' awareness of Rubella virus and media exposure, BCC materials and health belief; and finally
4. to identify social determinants of the awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects in the study areas.

DETERMINANTS OF SOCIAL AWARENESS REGARDING RUBELLA VIRUS

Research on Rubella virus and its effects on the foetus has been significant in the health promotion field all over the world. But there are very few works on the determinants of social awareness regarding the risks of Rubella virus on the foetus. In Bangladesh context, no sociological study has, hitherto, been conducted on this issue whereas numerous studies have been conducted on the determinants of awareness regarding HIV/ AIDS. That is why, the determinants in those studies on

HIV/ AIDS may lead to unearth those of social awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects in Bangladesh.

In a meta-analysis of 15 studies conducted on behaviour change concerning HIV/AIDS in developing countries, radio, television, video, print, and the internet were used to disseminate messages to produce awareness among the population (Bertrand *et al.*, 2006).^{6,17,22} The present study conducted on the factors of awareness regarding Rubella virus is also identical with the studies on those of HIV/AIDS. Health awareness campaigns are programs that disseminate educational messages to promote awareness or behaviour change to a targeted population through channels that reach a large audience. These channels are not merely limited to Radio, TV and internet (Bertrand *et al.*, 2006)⁶, but also these include leaflet, junk mail, posters, conference (Novella, 2004)¹⁷, newsletters, schools, and religious institutions (Green & Kreuter, 2005)¹¹⁻¹³. Numerous studies showed that media exposure is positively associated with health awareness (Sood & Nambiar, 2006).^{17,23} Some study showed that mass media campaigns tend to utilize three basic communication processes: awareness, instruction, and persuasion, so as to move the target audience toward the expected response. Awareness is also dependent on attitude making or change as a result of stock of knowledge or belief (Thompson, 2003).^{23,25} Cartagena *et al.* (2006)¹⁶ also found a significant relationship between the knowledge of students in the schools with the program and self-efficacy in health awareness. According to KAP²⁶ (Knowledge, Attitude and Practice) model, knowledge has an influence on attitude which in turn results in practice. And knowledge is dependent on income, education, media exposure and BCC materials. In Sable's work, health awareness seems to be associated with socio-cultural factors including attitude (beliefs, values, perceived risk of pregnancy, cognitive assessment/ acceptability of pregnancy, masculinity ideology, self esteem, and self efficacy), the influence of significant others (family, peers etc.) and socio-demographic factors (age, ethnicity, marital status, education and income) (Sable and M. Kay Libbus, 2008).^{10,22} According to HBM¹⁸ (Health Belief Model), health belief (which creates awareness) may be dependent on socio-demographic factors, perceived susceptibility (or diagnosing Rubella IgG and IgM), perceived severity, personal influence, media and reminders (Rosenstock, 1998).²¹

METHODOLOGY

The present study which is basically quantitative in nature, to collect the data, employs a survey questionnaire technique. Both structured and semi-

structured interview schedule was developed for data collection. Also qualitative technique like FGD was used to authenticate the quantitative results of the study. Data have been collected from six areas (Azimpur Colony, Kallyanpur Housing Estate, Banani, Tejgaon industrial area, Rupnagar Residential area and Fuller Road) of Dhaka city and Laxmirhat under Debiganj upazila of Panchagarh (The north most district of Bangladesh). A total of 390 women has been selected purposively for collecting the data, of which 240 women from 6 areas in Dhaka city each containing 40, and 150 women from Laxmirhat village. The selection of these respondents and areas was done taking into consideration of the homogeneous characteristics of the people in Bangladesh (see Table-2) and of time, effort and financial convenience. Hence, every individual of the study area has been considered as a unit of analysis. The variables and indicators were identified in terms of the conceptual framework of the study (See Figure-1). After the completion of the fieldwork (during December 2010), SPSS for Windows (Version 16) was used for coding data and getting the statistical findings.

Figure-1: Conceptual Framework of the Study.

* Awareness of the respondents regarding Rubella virus was measured by offering 18 statements (both positive and negative) to them to choose an option of 2 alternatives: *Agree*, and *disagree* coded as 1 and 0 respectively. Finally, those respondents who were able to choose correct option of at least 10 statements (more than 50 %) were considered as aware of Rubella virus.

STUDY FINDINGS

Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

The study showed that most of the respondents' ages (47.9 %) was ranged from 26 to 30 years in which the average age of the respondents was calculated as 30.42 years and standard deviation of 4.45 years (See Table 1).

Table-1: Socio-demographic features

Socio-demographic	n	%
Age* (in year)		
< 25	33	8.5
26-30	187	47.9
31-35	112	28.7
> 36	58	14.9
Total	390	100.0
Marital Status		
Married	340	87.2
Unmarried	50	12.8
Total	390	100.0
Pregnancy Status		
Pregnant	234	60.0
Non-Pregnant	156	40.0
Total	390	100.0
Family Type		
Patriarchy	379	97.2
Matriarchy	11	2.8
Total	390	100.0
Household Income**		
< 10,000	72	18.5
10,000-15,000	111	28.5
15,000-20,000	134	34.4
> 20,000	73	18.7
Total	390	100.0
Occupation		
Household Wife	203	52.1
Teaching	40	10.3
Job in Diagnostic Centre	17	4.4
Bank Job	101	25.9
Job in RMG Sector	29	7.4
Total	390	100.0

* Mean of Age= 30.42 & SD of Age = 4.45

** Mean of Household Income= Tk. 14,628; SD of Household Income= Tk. 5,202

Socio-demographic	n	%
Education		
Illiterate	23	5.9
Literate	367	94.1
Total	390	100.0
Household Size		
Up to 2	181	46.4
> 2	209	53.6
Total	390	100.0
Household Food security		
No	92	23.6
Yes	298	76.4
Total	390	100.0
Household Goods		
Radio	99	25.4
TV	31	7.9
Radio & TV	51	13.1
Radio, TV & Rich Furniture	106	27.2
Radio, TV, Rich Furniture & Refrigerator	66	16.9
Radio, TV, Rich Furniture, Air Conditioner & Refrigerator	13	3.3
None of them	24	6.2
Total	390	100.0
Ethnicity		
Bengali	262	67.2
Others	128	32.8
Total	390	100.0
Religion		
Islam	282	72.3
Others	108	27.7
Total	390	100.0

While 87.2 per cent respondents from study areas reported as they were married, 60 per cent of them were pregnant. In terms of family authority, there is a little practice of matriarchy in the study areas (2.8 %). The highest frequency of the respondents' monthly income was found between Tk. 15,000-20,000 with mean value of Tk. 14,628 and standard deviation of Tk. 5,202. The study found majority of the respondents as more or less educated and merely 5.9 per cent were calculated as illiterate. In terms of occupation, most of the respondents were found to be house wife, accounting for 52.1 per cent. Observing the data on household size (46.4 % have children < 2), it may be easily understood that the people of Bangladesh are now welcoming family planning program (See Table-1). More than 61.0 per cent middle class respondents have food security. In terms of household goods, the highest proportion of the respondents enjoyed TV, Radio and Rich furniture (27.2 %) and 6.2 per cent had no TV, Radio, rich furniture or refrigerator. Nearly 70 percent respondents were found Bengali and the percentage of Muslim was slight higher (72.3 %).

Social Awareness Regarding Rubella Virus

Awareness is defined as “the recognition of a topic or practice to trigger activation among audiences. Awareness encompasses attitude creation or change through knowledge gain or belief formation” (Thompson, 2003)¹⁶. The present study measures the respondents' awareness regarding Rubella virus by offering some 18 statements to them. Finally, it was found that most of the respondents from both urban and rural areas were not aware of Rubella virus (See Table 2).

Table- 2 Distribution of the Respondents by the Awareness regarding Rubella virus

Respondents' Level of Awareness	Dhaka City (N=240)		Laxmirhat (N=150)		Total (N=390)	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Aware of Rubella Virus	27	11.2	10	6.7	37	9.5
Unaware of Rubella Virus	213	88.8	140	93.3	353	90.5
Total	240	100.0	150	100.0	390	100.0

The Table 2 shows that 88.8 per cent from urban area and 93.3 per cent from rural area were found to be unaware of Rubella virus while a negligible portion of the respondents were aware of the virus. This statistic clearly shows that there is a great lack of health awareness in our country. Moreover, Bangladesh government has not introduced Rubella vaccine (MMR) program in our national immunization system, said

Ashrafunnessa et. al. At present, merely the rich families are being immunized privately for MMR vaccine is quite expensive. However, most of the respondents are not aware of the severity of the virus and its risks on the foetus. As an FGD participant puts it:

Though I have completed my graduation from Dhaka University, I know nothing about the virus and its risks on the unborn baby. In the eye of me, BTV should run the effective programs on different health problems prevalent in our country. Also, government of Bangladesh should, very soon, incorporate Rubella vaccination program in our national immunization system and should oblige BTV and private TV channels to telecast on the awareness building programs regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects (35 years old Najia Parvej, Field Work, Dhaka).

Association between Selected Socio-demographic Covariates and Awareness of Rubella Virus

Table 3 shows that awareness regarding Rubella virus is significantly related to different socio-demographic factors such as marital status (Phi= 0.12, P< 0.05), pregnancy status (Phi= 0.25, P< 0.01), household income (V= 0.49, P< 0.01), occupation (V= 0.70, P< 0.01), household size (Phi= 0.26, P< 0.01), household food security (Phi= 0.14, P< 0.01), household goods (V= 0.34, P< 0.01), ethnicity (Phi= 0.13, P< 0.05) and religion (Phi= 0.11, P< 0.05).

Table 3: Summary Table of Cramer's V and Phi Values* on Social Awareness regarding Rubella Virus by Socio-demographic Factors

Socio-demographic Factors	Social Awareness regarding Rubella Virus
Age	V = .10
Marital Status	Phi = .12 [‡]
Pregnancy Status	Phi = .25 [†]
Family Types	Phi = .05
Household Income	V = .49 [†]
Education	Phi = .08
Occupation	V = .70 [†]
Household Size	Phi = .26 [†]
Household Food Security	Phi = .14 [†]
Household Goods	V = .34 [†]
Ethnicity	Phi = .13 [‡]
Religion	Phi = .11 [‡]

* For the above nominal level variables, Cramer's V (for larger than 2x2 cross table) and Phi (for 2x2 cross table) tests are used (See Ref. 7 for details about the criteria on applying measures of association).

† Significant at the 0.01 level

‡ Significant at the 0.05 level

Surprisingly, in the present study, education was not found to be significantly related to the awareness regarding Rubella virus, followed by age cohort and family type. Notably, the awareness regarding Rubella virus varied from religion to religion. Muslims in Bangladesh seem to be less aware than other religions. While talking about this point, an FGD participant stated:

In spite of the presence of Rubella virus, perhaps, most of the doctors try to hide the severity of Rubella infection, if the patients are Muslims, taking into consideration of Muslim values of pregnancy termination while they suggest pregnancy termination if the patients are Hindus or Christians. Hence, Muslims are less aware of Rubella virus and its effects on the foetus (32 Years Old Andalib Hasan, Field Work, Laxmirhat).

Association between Media Exposure and Social Awareness Regarding Rubella Virus

Mass media plays a significant role in utilizing three basic communication processes: awareness, instruction, and persuasion. The present study also shows a significant influence of both electronic and print media on the awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects by examining respondent’s reading books, articles, magazines or newspapers (Phi= 0.44, P< 0.01) and watching health program on TV (Phi= 0.44, P< 0.01). Again, those who watched NTV program on the complications of Rubella virus consulted by Prof. Dr. Mehroz Alom Chowdhury, were found to be more aware of Rubella virus as indicated with Cramer’s Phi values of 0.89, P< 0.01 (see Table 4).

Table 4: Summary Table of Cramer’s V Statistics on Social Awareness regarding Rubella Virus by Selected Factors of Media Exposure and BCC* Materials

Factors of Media Exposure	Social Awareness Regarding Rubella Virus
Media Availability & Accessibility	Phi = .08
Reading Health Magazines/ Newspapers	Phi = .44†
Watching Health Program in TV	Phi = .44†
NTV Program on Rubella Virus by Mehroz Alom Chowdhury	Phi = .89†
BCC* Materials	Phi = .57†

†Significant at the 0.01 level
* BCC means Behaviour Change Communication

However, the respondents from the study areas reported that in spite of availability and accessibility, they could not enjoy health program related to Rubella virus and its risks on the foetus due to the lack of media reach in our country. As an FGD participant puts it:

We know nothing about Rubella virus and congenital birth defects on the foetus. We merely watch serials, cinema and special programs on different occasions and festivals. Actually, we have ever observed BTV program on Rubella virus and its complications (32 years old Razia Begum, Field Work, Dhaka).

Association between BCC Materials and Social Awareness regarding Rubella Virus

Health awareness is also associated with BCC materials like pamphlets, flyers, posters, conferences, flip charts etc., as reported by many researchers in this field. Table 4 shows that there is a significant association between Rubella awareness and BCC materials in the study areas with Cramer’s Phi values of 0.57 at significance level of 0.01 (See Table 4). Unfortunately, almost all of the respondents from study areas complain against the available posters or applying BCC materials. As an FGD participant puts it:

We do not find any poster or campaign on the awareness regarding Rubella virus and its severity. That is why, majority of the people in our country are unaware of this virus. GoB and NGOs should be more concerned with this dangerous virus to save the women and to protect birth defects, we think. We want to be emancipated from the attack of the virus. We are surprised at the reluctance of GoB in spite of availability of MMR vaccine. Our government should take initiatives to include MMR vaccine in our national immunization list (31 years old school teacher, Field Work, Dhaka).

Association between Perceived Susceptibility & Severity and Rubella Awareness

Though some studies based on HBM have been ineffective in third world or developing countries, the present study shows that Rubella awareness is strongly related to the perceived susceptibility (or the diagnosis of Rubella IgG & IgM) with Cramer’s Phi value of 0.78, P< 0.01 and to the perceived severity with that of 0.71, P< 0.01 (Table 5).

Table 5: Summary Table of Cramer’s V Statistics on Social Awareness regarding Rubella Virus by Perception of Susceptibility and Severity of Rubella Virus

Factors of Media Exposure	Social Awareness regarding Rubella Virus
Perceived Susceptibility or Diagnosis of Rubella IgG & IgM	Phi = .78†
Perceived Severity of Rubella Virus	Phi = .71†

† Significant at the 0.01 level

The above data seemed to be accurate when an FGD participant puts it:

My sister's in law, during pregnancy, was checked up in Rangpur medical due to severe complication. The blood tests on Rubella IgG and IgM antibodies were positive. Then, her pregnancy was terminated (28 years old Rokeya Akhter, Field Work, Laxmirhat).

Determinants of Awareness regarding Rubella Virus and Congenital Birth Defects in Bangladesh

In order to identify the determinants of awareness regarding Rubella virus and its risks on the foetus, finally a logistic regression model is developed. In this model, independent variables with more than two categories are called dummy variables. Table 6 shows the logistic regression results on awareness regarding Rubella virus.

Determinants	B	S.E.	Sig.	Exp(B)
Household Income	2.015	.850	.018	7.503
Food Security	2.456	1.774	.166	11.664
Reading Newspaper/ Health Magazine	-4.149	2.187	.058	.016
Watching NTV Program by Dr. Mehroz Alom Chowdhury*	6.508	1.606	.000	670.468
Perceived Susceptibility	5.102	2.394	.033	164.342
Perceived Severity	2.796	1.735	.107	16.385
Constant	-13.834	3.736	.000	.000

N= 390, Model $\lambda^2 = 213.983$, df= 6, $\alpha=.000$;
Cox and Snell $R^2 = .42$; Nagelkerke $R^2 = .91$

* Gynecologist and Obstetrics

By and large, this model is statistically significant with Cox and Snell $R^2 = 0.42$ and Nagelkerke $R^2 = .91$ ($P < 0.01$). Three variables including household income, perceived susceptibility and watching NTV Program by Mehroz Alom on Rubella complication were found to be significant as the determinants of awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects. This model also shows that watching NTV program on Rubella complication has been the single most significant determinant of Rubella awareness at the present study. Notably, the independent variables listed in the table-6 have been statistically significant with Cramer's Phi and V values. Let us now interpret the odds ratios of the significant determinants.

The 7.503 odds ratio for household income indicates that the respondents having monthly income more than Tk. 10,000 were 7.503 times more likely to be aware than those who earned below Tk. 10,000 monthly. The odds ratio of watching NTV program on Rubella complications consulted by Dr. Mehroz Alom Chowdhury indicates that those who watched such program was 670.47 times more likely to be aware of Rubella virus than those who did not. The analysis of odds ratio also indicates that the respondents who perceived susceptibility or diagnosed Rubella IgG and IgM were found to be 164.342 times more likely to be aware of Rubella virus than their counterpart.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of the present study was to explore the determinants of awareness regarding Rubella virus and congenital birth defects. After collecting data from the study areas and measuring the association between the dependent (social awareness regarding Rubella virus) and independent variables by Cramer's V and Phi statistics, it was found that the awareness was significantly related to marital status, pregnancy status, household income, occupation, household size, food security, household goods, ethnicity, religion, reading health magazines or newspapers, watching health program on TV, BCC materials, perceived susceptibility (the acceptance of diagnosis of Rubella IgG and IgM) and perceived severity of ill health condition for being caught by Rubella virus.

But, when a binary logistic regression model is developed in order to filter the results of Cramer's V and Phi statistics, only three determinants became significant. They are household income, perceived susceptibility and watching NTV program by Mehroz Alom on Rubella complication.

However, since the present study, due to its nature of both area and respondent selection, is not nationally representative and generalizable, the future researchers in this arena are recommended to conduct the studies using probability sampling. Hence, GoB and NGOs should provide the necessary fund to conduct the rigorous studies on this issue. Despite the limitation of area and respondent selection, the present study claims that the study findings may be consistent with most of the areas of Bangladesh since the characteristics of the respondents and the people of other areas in the country are more or less homogeneous. The study, therefore, gives some recommendations. *First* of all, TV channels in the country should disseminate the severity of Rubella virus and its aftermaths on the foetus. *Secondly*, Bangladesh government should run the awareness campaigns regarding Rubella virus through both electronic

and print media. *Thirdly*, GoB should also take the proper initiatives to include Rubella vaccine in our national immunization list. *Finally*, sociologists of Bangladesh should conduct the studies on this issue, and arrange the seminars, symposium, workshop and rally in order to create the awareness among the people all over the country.

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